

Association between Environment Pollution Exposure and Exacerbation in Patients with Interstitial Lung Disease

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Abstract:

Background: Interstitial lung disease (ILD) refers to a group of chronic lung conditions characterized by inflammation and fibrosis of the lung parenchyma. Exacerbations in ILD are associated with rapid lung function decline, increased hospitalizations, and higher mortality rates. Environmental pollution, known to exacerbate other respiratory diseases, has been increasingly linked to worsening outcomes in ILD patients.

Aim: To assess the association between environmental pollution exposure and exacerbation in patients with interstitial lung disease.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted involving 50 patients diagnosed with ILD. Patients were categorized based on their exposure to high- or low-pollution areas. Data on exacerbation frequency, patient demographics, and clinical history were collected from medical records. Statistical analysis was achieved using SPSS version 24.0, with chi-square tests and logistic regression used to assess the relationship between pollution exposure and exacerbations.

Results: Of the 50 patients, 56% lived in high-pollution areas and experienced significantly higher rates of exacerbations (2.3 ± 0.7 per year) compared to patients in low-pollution areas (1.2 ± 0.5 per year) ($p < 0.001$). Logistic regression analysis showed that high pollution exposure was associated with a 3.8-fold increased risk of exacerbations (OR 3.8; 95% CI: 1.7–8.3; $p = 0.001$). The findings remained statistically significant even after adjusting for confounders such as age, gender, smoking status, and disease duration.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates a significant association between environmental pollution exposure and increased ILD exacerbations. Patients exposed to higher pollution levels experienced more frequent and severe exacerbations, suggesting that pollution is a major modifiable risk factor for ILD exacerbation.

Recommendations: Efforts should be made to reduce pollution exposure in ILD patients, particularly in high-risk areas. Public health policies aimed at improving air quality could substantially benefit individuals with chronic respiratory diseases, including ILD.

Keywords: Interstitial Lung Disease, Exacerbation, Environmental Pollution, Air Quality, Respiratory Disease, Public Health Interventions.

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Introduction

Interstitial lung disease (ILD) encompasses a diverse group of lung disorders characterized by varying degrees of inflammation and fibrosis affecting the lung parenchyma. ILD can lead to progressive scarring of lung tissue, reducing respiratory function and causing significant morbidity and mortality. Exacerbations in ILD, defined as acute deteriorations of respiratory status, are particularly detrimental, often leading to accelerated lung function decline, hospitalizations, and increased mortality rates [1]. Understanding the risk factors associated with ILD exacerbations

is crucial for improving patient outcomes and guiding public health interventions.

Environmental pollution has long been recognized as a significant factor contributing to the worsening of chronic respiratory diseases, such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). In recent years, increasing evidence has emerged linking environmental pollution exposure to the exacerbation of ILD [2]. Airborne pollutants, including particulate matter (PM), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and ozone (O₃), are well-known for their harmful effects on the respiratory system. These pollutants can trigger

oxidative stress and inflammation, exacerbating underlying lung diseases like ILD [3].

Recent studies have shown that individuals with ILD are particularly vulnerable to the effects of environmental pollutants. Research demonstrated that patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), a common subtype of ILD, experienced significantly higher rates of exacerbations and hospitalizations in areas with elevated air pollution levels [4]. Similarly, the findings of a study suggested a correlation between long-term exposure to air pollution and accelerated lung function decline in ILD patients [5]. Given these findings, pollution exposure is emerging as a modifiable risk factor for ILD exacerbations.

However, while several studies have focused on the impact of pollution on IPF, there is limited research examining the broader ILD population, which includes other subtypes such as nonspecific interstitial pneumonia (NSIP) and hypersensitivity pneumonitis (HP). Furthermore, the majority of existing studies have been conducted in North America and Europe, with fewer investigations in regions with higher levels of air pollution, such as Asia and developing countries.

The study aims to assess the association between environmental pollution exposure and exacerbation in patients with interstitial lung disease.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study was carried out over a one-year period, from January 2023 to December 2023, at the Government Hospital for Chest & Communicable Diseases, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India. The study included a total of 50 patients diagnosed with ILD, who met the inclusion criteria during the study period after approval of ethical committee.

Inclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria consisted of patients aged 18 years and older with a confirmed diagnosis of ILD, who had documented exposure to environmental pollution during the study period. Patients were required to have undergone follow-up for at least six months prior to enrollment in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Exclusion criteria included patients with a history of occupational lung disease, those with incomplete medical records, or

individuals who had undergone lung transplantation during the study period. Patients who had other comorbidities like heart failure or COPD were also excluded to reduce confounding factors.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, medical records were reviewed by two independent clinicians who were blinded to the outcomes. Data selection was based solely on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from medical records and included demographic information, clinical history, environmental pollution exposure history, and ILD exacerbation episodes. Pollution exposure data were gathered through recorded patient history regarding residence location, proximity to industrial areas, or high-traffic zones. The severity and frequency of ILD exacerbations were noted based on clinical findings and hospital admissions.

Procedure: Medical records were reviewed to identify relevant information. A systematic chart review was performed to extract clinical and demographic data, which were entered into a standardized data collection form. The information was then coded and categorized for statistical analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using SPSS 24.0. The clinical and demographic characteristics were gathered using descriptive statistics. Chi-square tests were employed to assess the connection between environmental pollution and ILD exacerbations, whereas t-tests assessed continuous variables. Logistic regression analysis was used to compute ORs with 95% CI and account for covariates. Significance was 0.05 or less.

Results

A total of 50 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of ILD were included in this study. The mean age of the participants was 62.4 ± 9.3 years, with 40% (n=20) being male and 60% (n=30) female. The majority of patients (n=34, 68%) resided in urban areas, with a significant portion (n=28, 56%) living in regions of high industrial pollution or traffic density. The mean duration of the disease since diagnosis was 4.8 ± 2.6 years.

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics

Characteristics	Total (N=50)
Mean Age (years)	62.4 ± 9.3
Gender	
- Male	20 (40%)
- Female	30 (60%)
Urban Residency	34 (68%)
Rural Residency	16 (32%)
Exposure to High Pollution Areas	28 (56%)
Duration of ILD (years)	4.8 ± 2.6

Frequency of ILD Exacerbations: Among the 50 patients, 32 (64%) experienced at least one exacerbation during the study period. The mean number of exacerbations was 1.8 ± 0.9 per patient per year. Patients exposed to high levels of

environmental pollution (n=28) had a higher mean exacerbation rate of 2.3 ± 0.7 per year, compared to 1.2 ± 0.5 exacerbations per year in patients residing in low-pollution areas (n=22). This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Exacerbation rates based on pollution exposure levels.

Exacerbations	High Pollution (n=28)	Low Pollution (n=22)	p-value
Mean Exacerbations per Year	2.3 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 0.5	<0.001
Patients with ≥ 1 Exacerbation	22 (78.6%)	10 (45.5%)	0.008

Association Between Pollution Exposure and ILD Exacerbation: A strong association was found between environmental pollution exposure and the risk of exacerbations in ILD patients. Logistic regression analysis, adjusting for confounding factors such as age, gender, smoking

status, and disease duration, showed that patients exposed to high levels of pollution were 3.8 times more likely to experience an exacerbation compared to those in low-pollution areas (OR 3.8; 95% CI: 1.7–8.3; $p = 0.001$).

Table 3: Logistic regression analysis

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
High Pollution Exposure	3.8	1.7 – 8.3	0.001
Age (per year increase)	1.02	0.98 – 1.06	0.23
Male Gender	1.5	0.7 – 3.2	0.29
Smoking Status	1.8	0.8 – 3.9	0.14
Disease Duration (years)	1.05	0.92 – 1.19	0.40

Sensitivity Analysis: In a sensitivity analysis restricted to non-smokers (n=30), the association between pollution exposure and exacerbation remained statistically significant (OR 3.4; 95% CI: 1.4–7.9; $p = 0.004$), further supporting the robustness of the results.

Discussion

The current study involved 50 patients with interstitial lung disease (ILD), with a mean age of 62.4 years, and 56% of these patients lived in regions with high pollution exposure, such as industrial or traffic-heavy areas. Similar findings were noted in a population-based study by Chen et al. (2020), where air pollution, specifically PM_{2.5}, was significantly associated with the development of ILD in patients with connective tissue diseases (CTD), indicating that individuals in polluted areas are at higher risk of disease development and progression [6]. Likewise, Singh & Singh (2021) showed that ILD patients in highly polluted urban areas were more susceptible to exacerbations, particularly those exposed to nitrogen dioxide and particulate matter [7]. Manfredi et al. (2019) further demonstrated that patients with ILD secondary to systemic rheumatic diseases were more prone to exacerbations when exposed to urban pollution, underscoring the role of environmental pollutants as a key risk factor [8].

The mean exacerbation rate was 1.8 per year, with patients in high-pollution regions experiencing 2.3 exacerbations annually, compared to 1.2 in low-pollution areas ($p < 0.001$). Harari et al. (2020)

conducted a systematic review that supported these results, showing that patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) had a higher frequency of exacerbations when exposed to elevated air pollution levels, particularly PM₁₀ and NO₂, with similar statistical significance ($p < 0.001$) [9]. Additionally, Cao et al. (2019) found that acute exacerbations in fibrosing ILD were more prevalent in urban areas with high pollution levels, further supporting the association between pollution and exacerbation frequency [10]. The study by Lee et al. (2021) also noted a higher rate of acute exacerbation in ILD patients exposed to elevated levels of environmental pollutants, with interleukin-6 (IL-6) acting as a biomarker to predict these exacerbations [11].

The logistic regression analysis showed that patients exposed to high pollution had 3.8 times the risk of exacerbation (OR 3.8; 95% CI: 1.7–8.3; $p = 0.001$). Kolb et al. (2018) also identified pollution as an independent risk factor for exacerbations in progressive fibrosing ILD, with a similarly elevated odds ratio (OR 3.6; 95% CI: 1.5–7.9; $p = 0.002$), indicating that pollution exposure significantly worsens ILD outcomes [12]. Moreover, Singh & Singh (2021) confirmed pollution's impact as an independent risk factor, particularly highlighting its role in increasing oxidative stress and inflammation in ILD patients [7]. Similarly, Lee et al. (2021) found that increased levels of IL-6, linked to pollution exposure, were predictive of higher rates of

exacerbation, further reinforcing the role of pollutants in aggravating ILD [11].

After adjusting for confounders such as age, gender, smoking status, and disease duration, the association between pollution and exacerbation remained significant (OR 3.8; $p=0.001$). Similarly, in the study by Harari et al. (2020), the authors adjusted for smoking and other potential confounders, yet pollution exposure remained a significant predictor of poor outcomes in patients with fibrotic ILDs [9]. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis in the current study excluding smokers showed that pollution remained the primary driver of exacerbations (OR 3.4; 95% CI: 1.4–7.9; $p=0.004$), consistent with findings from Cao et al. (2019) where pollution's impact on exacerbations was evident even after excluding smokers [10].

The current study's findings, which highlight pollution as a significant risk factor for ILD exacerbations, align with conclusions from multiple studies. For instance, Chen et al. (2020) found that limiting exposure to air pollutants, particularly particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide, could mitigate ILD progression and reduce exacerbation rates in vulnerable populations [6]. These consistent findings underscore the need for targeted interventions, such as improving air quality in urban areas and minimizing patient exposure to pollutants, as also suggested by Singh & Singh (2021) [7].

Conclusion

This retrospective study provides compelling evidence that environmental pollution is a significant risk factor for exacerbations in patients with interstitial lung disease. These findings highlight the need for public health interventions aimed at reducing pollution exposure in vulnerable populations, especially those with chronic respiratory conditions. Further prospective studies are recommended to confirm these findings and to explore potential mechanisms linking pollution exposure to ILD exacerbation.

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